

REPORT:

A2.1.4: Guideline describing relevant characteristics for the development of a universal connector for the integration of off-chip sensors and actuators identified in A2.1.1

Work package 2

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Activity number	Activity description	Participants (Lead in bold)
A2.1.4 M12	Micronit, together with METU, INESC MN, and IPQ will define a guideline describing relevant characteristics for the development of a universal connector for the integration of off-chip sensors/actuators identified in A2.1.1 and that cannot be integrated as described in A2.1.3. Input will be received from 20NRM02 MFMET WP3.	Micronit , METU, INESC MN, IPQ

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1. Scope

This guideline defines the key requirements and desirable characteristics of a universal microfluidic connector for integrating off-chip sensors and actuators identified in the MFMET database (A2.1.1, (MFMET database with sensors and actuators) **Error! Reference source not found.**) that cannot be integrated using the approaches described in A2.1.3 (Guideline for the Integration of Sensors, Actuators, and Fluidic Components in Microfluidic Devices) **Error! Reference source not found...** It focuses on fluidic interfaces based on tubing and Luer-type connections used between external components and microfluidic devices.

The guideline addresses the design considerations required to ensure interoperability, reliability, leak-free operation, ease of use, manufacturability, and compatibility with existing standards. Relevant aspects include geometric standardization, fluidic performance, material compatibility, mechanical robustness, contamination control, user experience, and manufacturing constraints.

The scope is limited to second-level microfluidic connectors as defined in ISO 10991:2023 and does not include electrical, optical, or hybrid fluidic-electrical-optical connectors, nor permanent connection methods such as adhesive bonding. The guideline does not prescribe a specific connector design but provides criteria to support the development and evaluation of connector solutions that promote standardized and interoperable microfluidic systems.

2. Requirements and Design Considerations for a Universal Connector for Off-Chip Sensors and Actuators

2.1 Connectors for sensors and actuators listed in A2.1.1

The scope of this guideline is restricted to integration of off-chip sensors and actuators identified in A2.1.1 that cannot be integrated as described in A2.1.3. The fluid connections of the components listed in A2.1.1 fall in two categories: tubing and Luer connectors. More specifically, the following connections are listed:

Tubing:

- Fittings compatible with 1/16-inch and/or 1/32-inch outer diameter (semi)rigid tubing;
- Silicone tubing;
- Swagelok fitting for 6 mm outer diameter tubing (Bronkhorst flow sensors);
- Pneumatic push-in fitting for 4 mm outer diameter tubing (Fluigent pressure regulators).

Luer:

- Luer, Luer lock or mini Luer fitting.

In addition to fluid connections, sensors and actuators could also require electrical or optical connections. Hybrid or mixed media connectors that combine fluids, electrical and optical signals are out of scope for this document. Therefore, this report particularly considers the microfluidic connectors as defined in ISO10991:2023. The universal microfluidic connector addressed by this guideline operates as a second-level connection (ISO10991:2023, 3.3.2). Relevant connection types include ferrule connections, push-in connections, Luer and mini Luer connectors, and multi-connectors. Adhesive connections are considered permanent and are therefore out of scope.

2.2 Integration of sensors, actuators and fluidic components in microfluidic devices described in A2.1.3

Report A2.1.3 provides high level guidelines for the integration of sensors, actuators, and fluidic components in microfluidic devices. The use of connectors for tubes can be considered as microfluidic connectors available is many variants that differ in thread size, materials, and mating interface geometry (conical or flat face ferrule connection, Figure 1) or flared connection.

Luer connectors are not mentioned in the report but these can be converted to tubes with a fluidic adapter (see Figure 2 for examples). Following this reasoning, a universal microfluidic connector is not strictly required for any of the sensors or actuators listed in A2.1.1, but a guideline might still be of value.

Universal connections are important in microfluidics because the chip-to-world interface is a major challenge, requiring reliable, leak-free connections between microdevices and external systems. Standardized connectors improve interoperability and enable plug-and-play operation, while widely used solutions such as Luer fittings provide robust, reproducible interfaces [4].

Figure 1: Examples of connectors for 1/16-inch laboratory tubes. a) ferrule connection with conical sealing face, b) ferrule connection with flat-bottom sealing face. Reproduced from [1].

Figure 2: Various types of Luer-to-tubing adapters. a) image from IDEX health & science, b) image from Reichelt Chemietechnik.

3. Relevant characteristics of a universal connector for the integration of off-chip sensors and actuators

When designing a universal connector many properties can be considered. These include for example:

1. Geometric and dimensional standardization:

- Port geometry (diameter, depth, and surface shape of the mating area) compatible with standardized dimensions defined in ISO 22916:2022;
- Compact footprint compatible with standard port pitch (ISO 22916:2022), enabling use in multi-port configurations;
- Compatible with tubes of standard outer diameters (e.g., 1/32", 1/16" and 1/8" OD).

2. Fluidic connection performance:

- Leak-proof sealing up to the maximum possible operating pressure;
- Hydrodynamic resistance negligible compared to that of the connected device;
- Minimal internal volume with near zero dead volume;
- Flow path geometry that does not disrupt single-phase, multi-phase, or droplet flows;
- Low mechanical compliance, to avoid deformation of the connector body under pressure that would introduce unintended volumetric buffering and distort flow.

3. Material compatibility:

- Compatible with both rigid substrates (e.g., glass, silicon, hard thermoplastics such as PMMA, COC) and soft substrates (e.g., PDMS, elastomers), accounting for differences in surface compliance and sealing behaviour;
- Materials in contact with the fluid shall be biocompatible for applications involving biological samples, cell culture, or in vitro diagnostics;
- Resistance to solvents commonly used in microfluidic workflows, including alcohols (ethanol, isopropanol) and aqueous buffers;
- Thermally stable across the operating temperature range of the intended range of applications (indicatively up to 100°C; higher if autoclave compatibility is required).

4. Mechanical robustness:

- Capable of withstanding a minimum number of mating cycles consistent with the intended use (e.g., order of hundreds for reusable lab connectors);
- Resistant to accidental disconnection under vibration levels typical of laboratory equipment (e.g., pumps, shakers, centrifuges);
- Locking mechanism that prevents accidental disconnection under operating pressure and handling forces (e.g., Luer-like twist, snap fit, magnetic clamp, or threaded connection);
- Sealing integrity and locking stability maintained under cyclic pressure loading from pulsatile flow sources (e.g., peristaltic pumps) and pressure transients;
- Resistance to creep and relaxation of polymer parts.

5. Cross-contamination control:

- Flow path with smooth surfaces and no sharp corners or recesses, to prevent particles, cells, or biological material from getting trapped;
- Low adsorption of analytes, reagents, and biological molecules to wetted surfaces, to avoid sample loss and measurement bias;
- Low leachable content from connector materials into the fluid, to avoid chemical interference with measurements or biological assays;
- Clean disconnect / non-drip features;
- Compatible with at least one validated sterilization method (e.g., autoclaving, ethanol flushing, or gamma irradiation).

6. User experience:

- Tool-free connect and disconnect;
- Insertion force low enough to allow connection by hand;
- Clear confirmation when the connection is made, through tactile feedback (e.g., audible click) and/or visual cues (e.g., colour coding, keyed orientation);
- Self-alignment features (e.g., tapered inlets, alignment pins, keyed geometries) to guide correct insertion without requiring precise manual positioning;
- Connector geometry that physically prevents incorrect connections between incompatible inlet and outlet types;

- Option for a multi-connector design that handles several fluid lines simultaneously in a single connection action.

7. Manufacturing constraints:

- Compatibility with scalable manufacturing methods such as injection molding;
- Low part count;
- No manufacturing steps requiring specialized equipment beyond standard polymer processing.

8. Alignment to existing standards:

A universal connector should be compatible with, or help converge to, emerging standards:

- ISO 80369-1:2025 (small-bore connectors);
- Port dimensions and pitches defined in ISO 22916:2022;
- Open microfluidics standards from academic consortia.

4. Summary

This guideline reviewed the requirements and considerations for the development of a universal microfluidic connector intended for the integration of off-chip sensors and actuators identified in the MFMET database. Although the components considered can generally be interconnected through existing tubing, fitting, and Luer-based solutions, the lack of harmonized interfaces remains a challenge for interoperability, system integration, and the realization of plug-and-play microfluidic platforms.

To address these challenges, a set of relevant characteristics for universal connectors was identified, covering geometric standardization, fluidic performance, material compatibility, mechanical robustness, contamination control, user experience, manufacturing constraints, and alignment with existing standards. Particular emphasis was placed on achieving reliable, leak-free operation, low dead volume, compatibility with common microfluidic connection formats, and ease of use without compromising performance.

The analysis indicates that no single connector technology currently satisfies all possible application requirements. Nevertheless, the characteristics described in this guideline provide a framework for the evaluation, selection, and future development of connector solutions capable of supporting a broad range of microfluidic devices and external sensors and actuators. Adoption of these principles can contribute to improved interoperability, increased system reliability, and greater standardization across the microfluidics community.

5. References

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- [7] ISO 10991:2023 - Microfluidics — Vocabulary